

Translation from Bulgarian

Covid-19 - The Big Mistake

PARS /Pulmovascular acute respiratory syndrome or
Pulmonary hypertensive acute respiratory syndrome/.

A new syndrome for the new virus.

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It is time to look at Covid-19 as a known disease and recognize our mistakes. The biggest one of these is the receptor through which we believe the virus invades and its location in the body - angiotensin II receptor type 2 and not simply angiotensin II receptor.

Most of the effects of the AT2 hormone occur via AT2 R1. AT2R2 has almost reverse physiological effects and a different area in the body - intestinum, myometrium, kidney and others.

The signalling pathways of AT2 run through two types of dephosphorylations and express themselves in apoptosis, antiproliferation, differentiation, VASODILATATION, tissue regeneration. When the virus enters these receptors, it practically has an inhibitory effect and causes microvascular vasoconstriction, NO /nitric oxide/ deficiency, increase of endothelin-1 and others, which affects the lungs, but also other organs, and is accompanied by increased coagulation. The interaction of endothelin-1 with PAI1 is of key importance. The myeloperoxidase damage to the hemoglobin in the microvessels has yet to be investigated.

The place of the action - the pulmonary arterioles. We should therefore consider hypooxygenation by the severely ill patients such as pulmonary hypertension (PH) of microvascular type with the PH specific ground glass X-ray images and with the age distribution, complication factors and their treatment specific to the PH disease. The damage to the respiratory epithelium is not significant for the shortness of breath.

I emphasize that the effects of AT2R2 do not rule out viral respiratory damage via other receptors that are similar to the viruses known so far. If the disease does not lead to death, the exit from the situation of microhypertension is successful with appropriate treatment by lowering the viral pressure on AT2R2. This view of the disease will allow correct prediction during the mild course at the beginning of the illness and will give explainable new meaning to the role of RAS's antihypertensive drugs. I dare to assume that the ARB drugs will reduce the disease to acceptably mild for those who take them.

This view of Covid-19 as PARS /Pulmovascular acute respiratory syndrome/, a new syndrome, does not exclude our attention to the other complications of the viral infection /bacterial superinfections, cytokine storm, cardiac arrhythmia etc. / and their predictors.

Used sources:

The Role of the AT2 Receptor in Hypertension, Helmy M. Siragy
<https://academic.oup.com/ajh/article-abstract/13/S3/62S/164904>